

Performance Analysis of Stegano Data With Improved LSB Substitution using Horse Step Algorithm and Advanced Encryption Standard

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Abstract

The two popular methods of transmitting secret information in a very secure way are Cryptography and Steganography. Cryptography scrambles information so it cannot be comprehended while Steganography shrouds the message so that it cannot be visible. In this method, first, a message is encrypted using an algorithm based on the AES cryptographic algorithm or Horse step algorithm which is then embedded inside an image using the method of Least Significant Bit (LSB) substitution. Digital pictures usually have an oversized quantity of redundant information; thus, it is attainable to cover the message within the image file. Image steganography deals with exploiting the restricted power of human vision where the message is hidden within the LSB of the image data. This embedding technique relies on the very fact that the LSB bit in an image will be thought of as random noise, and consequently, they turn out to be less receptive to any change in the image. Cryptography and Steganography combinedly can enhance the protection of the info embedded. This combinable methodology can satisfy wants like capability, security, and hardiness for secure knowledge transmission over an open channel.

Keywords: structural similarity, mean square error, peak signal-to-noise ratio, encryption, decryption key, cover image, stego image, structural similarity

Introduction

From the dawn of civilization to the highly networked societies, information exchange has always been an important part of our lives. In the current digital era, the fast escalations in digital multimedia systems and networks have sealed ways for individuals around to accumulate, utilize, and share multimedia system info. Radio communication, telephone communication, mobile communication, etc. are the means of communication in today's world. With the expansion of the network, the security of information has become a significant concern, and therefore data-concealing techniques have attracted folks around the globe (Zhou et al., 2016). Such speedy advances in technology have additionally given rise to security threats to people and organizations. Hence, data security has evolved as a vital and pressing issue not just for people but for businesses and governments too. In this research, data security is preserved with cryptography and steganography.

Cryptography and Steganography are two popular methods of sending secret information securely. One shrouds the presence of the message while the other twists the message itself by distortion. These are popular methods that control messages keeping in mind the end goal to figure out or shroud their reality

separately (Zhou et al., 2016). Steganography is the art of imparting a message in a way that conceals the presence of the correspondence (Nurwhaju et al., 2016) Cryptography scrambles information so it cannot be comprehended while Steganography shrouds the message so that it cannot be visible.

Data hiding techniques have been challenging nowadays for digital forensic investigators (Zhou et al., 2016). To ensure that knowledge is secured and does not attend unplanned destinations, the concept of knowledge activity came up to guard a chunk of data (Rahate & Rothe, 2014). The Internet provides a communication technique to distribute data to the lots. Therefore, confidentiality and knowledge integrity are needed to safeguard against unauthorized access and use (Singh et al., 2007). Steganography and cryptography are two distinctive data-concealing systems, where the message is changed to make it an important cloud to malevolent people who catch it. Steganography depends on concealing messages in unsuspected mixed media information and is for the most part utilized as a part of mystery correspondence between recognized gatherings (Bahl & Girdhar, 2012). The file formats having a higher degree of redundancy are more suitable for steganography. Digital images

are widely used as cover objects as they bear massive amounts of redundant data where steganography can be used. Cryptography simply obscures the integrity of the data so that it does not belong to anyone except the creator and the recipient (Li et al., 2011). Privacy is assured by Cryptography while secrecy can be achieved through Steganography. “Steganography and cryptography are both used to ensure data confidentiality”(Ahmad et al., 2012). However, steganography differs from cryptography in the sense that cryptography focuses on keeping the contents of a message secret whereas steganography focuses on keeping the existence of a message secret (Morkel et al., 2005). Thus, cryptography shows communication between parties in a secure way while steganography makes secret messages invisible to others.

Literature Review

Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), also known as Rijndael is a specification for the encryption of electronic data established by the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in 2001. It is based on the Rijndael cipher developed by two Belgian cryptographers, Joan Daemen and Vincent Rijmen. It has been adopted by the U.S. government and is now used worldwide. RIJNDAEL is based on a design principle known as a substitution-permutation network, a combination of both substitution and permutation and is fast in both software and hardware. This research is based on the cryptography technique designed by Nawayoga, Bambang H, and Iwan Iwut where they introduced a novel method of cryptography known as Horse Step Algorithm. This method of cryptography exploits a 2D matrix to encrypt messages. The flexible key, excellent security, efficiency, and suitability for steganography are some of the features of this algorithm(Nurwhaju et al., 2016). Cryptography is not only science but also art for securing messages. Cryptography becomes interesting due to flexible keys (Ahmad et al., 2012). Zhi and Fen (Morkel et al., 2005) proposed a method of LSB image steganography, LSB

in which a secret message was inserted in a selected portion of the image not in a fixed or predefined manner which makes steganalysis difficult. According to Zhang et al. (in (Li et al., 2011))“a new method of LSB steganalysis is based on the statistical distribution of pixel difference in the spatial domain which can be done on high-resolution images based on the difference of zero and non-zero values of pixels and also finds the error which is used to determine the steganographic features.” Here, Laplacian distribution is used. Further Li et al.(Ahmad et al., 2012) proposed a method for uplifting wavelet transform images with LSB Information Hiding algorithm. Results proved to be particularly good security for attacks done invisibly.

Methodology

An image is considered a common type of digital media for steganography as it bears a tremendous amount of unwanted or redundant data. Image steganography deals with exploiting the restricted power of human vision where the message is hidden within the LSB of the image data. This embedding technique relies on the very fact that the LSB bit in an image will be thought of as random noise, and consequently, they turn out to be less receptive to any change in the image. To improve the limit of image steganography and give an indistinct stego picture to human vision, a system for concealing extensive volumes of information is proposed in images by consolidating cryptography and steganography while causing negligible perceptual corruption and taking care of the issue of unauthorized data access.

To increase the security of this data, steganography can be embedded with cryptography.

In this method, first, a message is encrypted using an algorithm based on a cryptographic algorithm then the encrypted message is embedded inside an image using the LSB embedding method as LSB substitution alone is not sufficient. The combination of methods will increase security.

Figure 1

Block diagram of system overview

Comparison

Digital images often have a large amount of redundant data and for this reason, it is possible to hide messages inside image files. Image steganography is about exploiting the limited power of the human visual system where information is hidden in the least significant bit of the image data. This embedding method is because the least significant bit in an image can be thought of as random noise, and consequently, they become less responsive to any change in the image.

Usually, the invisibility of the hidden message is calculated in terms of the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR).

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \frac{255^2}{MSE} \dots(i)$$

Where mean square error (MSE)

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y+c_1)(2\sigma_{xy}+c_2)}{(\mu_x^2+\mu_y^2+c_1)(\sigma_x^2+\sigma_y^2+c_2)} \dots(iii)$$

The similarity between the original message and the distorted message can be evaluated using the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM).

Where,

μ_x is average of x

μ_y is average of y

σ_x^2 is variance of x

σ_y^2 is variance of y

σ_{xy} is the co-variance of x and y

c_1 and c_2 are the constants

The result also showed a negligible difference between the original image and the stego image. The experimental results performed on hiding 4 KB of useful data on 80 KB image size showed that compared with LSB Substitution, Improved LSB substitution has lower MSE and higher PSNR along with higher SSIM. This shows that Improved Least Significant Bit substitution is an improvement over simple Least Significant Bit substitution.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2

Comparative analysis of Mean Square Error

Figure 3

Comparative analysis of Peak Signal to Noise Ratio

Figure 4*Comparative analysis of Structural Similarity*

Figure 2 gives the mean square error of the original image along with the message hidden image (stego image) where distortion can be seen as more prone to LSB substitution which leads to higher PSNR of the image using improved LSB substitution. Similarly, Figure 4 shows the structural similarity of the original and stego image which proves that improved LSB substitution has less distortion than the LSB substitution.

Conclusion

In this paper, an efficient image steganography algorithm has been made more secure with the help of cryptographic algorithms based on AES and HSA cryptographic algorithms. The reason behind choosing AES and HSA is security as both provide excellent security. AES is the fastest cryptographic algorithm while HSA is the algorithm for variable length key facility. Also, HSA performs great for higher data sizes. So, among lots of cryptographic algorithms, these two are among the best. The combinational method will increase the security of the data embedded. With the negligible difference between the original image and the stego image, the embedded information can be transmitted securely. The increase in complexity level in retrieving information further enhances the security of secret data in improved LSB substitution. Compared with LSB Substitution, Improved LSB substitution has lower MSE and higher PSNR along with high SSIM which is shown in Table 1. This shows that Improved Least Significant Bit substitution is an improvement over simple Least Significant Bit substitution. Hence,

this combinational methodology provides resistance against various visual and statistical attacks.

Although separately using either cryptography or steganography provides security, combinational methods would add multiple security levels. The HSA algorithm has limitations regarding lower bits of data which can be made faster in the future. In this research, cryptographic algorithms are used separately but, in the future, both the algorithms can be implemented together but in a random way. Other methods of cryptography and steganography can be used in the future for more data security.

Limitations

Data-hiding techniques have been used for the transmission of secret messages for decades. Ensuring data security is of high concern for users. Since the LSB of the image is prone to error, the system can be made more secure by introducing various error recovery techniques. Likewise, for hiding secret information, a larger image size is required which can be minimized by replacing other bits at the cost of effective appearance on an image. One of the limitations of symmetric cryptography is the difficulty in transmitting the secret key. Also, the data size plays a significant role during data secrecy as higher bits of data need to be transmitted. So, for this purpose, AES operates poorly while HSA is the best option. But HSA too has some limitations for smaller bits which can be made faster in the future. The method can be defined as secured communication providing a high level of security.

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